

APPLICATION OF RADIAL AND CIRCULAR REINFORCEMENTS FOR CFRP BOLTED JOINTS

Toshifumi Fujii¹, Kazuo Nakajima¹, Yasuhiko Iwasaki¹
Yusuke Osugi², Shun Kudo², Naoki Mori² and Takayuki Kusaka²

¹Shikibo Ltd., 1500-5 Shibaharaminami Higashiomi Shiga 527-8577 Japan,
<http://www.shikibo.co.jp>

²Ritsumeikan University, 1-1-1 Nojihigashi Kusatsu Shiga 525-8577 Japan,
<http://www.ritsumei.ac.jp>

Keywords: Bolted joints, Failure modes, Hole positions, R-layer, C-layer

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a novel reinforcement technique using radial and circular layers (R-layer, C-layer) was studied to improve the strength and reliability of bolted joints, especially for large-scale composite parts. In addition, the normalized position of the bolt hole, e/d , was also discussed. The experimental result demonstrated that the R-layer was effective in improving both of the initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , and the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} , but the C-layer was effective only in improving the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} for the specimen with $e/d = 3$. The result demonstrated that the C-layer prevented the shear failure caused by the inadequate geometry of the bolt hole, resulting in the improvement of the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} , but the R-layer was not effective in preventing the shear mode failure for the specimen with $e/d = 1$. The numerical result demonstrated that the effectiveness of the R-layer against bearing mode failure for the specimen with $e/d = 3$, and the effectiveness of the C-layer against shear mode failure for the specimen with $e/d = 1$.

1 INTRODUCTION

CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics) are extensively used for aerospace structures owing to their excellent specific strength, stiffness, and other characteristics. However, some drawbacks have been recognized regarding the use of the joining technique of composite materials due to the complexity of the mechanical properties or fracture behavior.

Figure 1 schematically shows typical failure modes of bolt-jointed composite plates. The failure mode in Figure 1 (a) shows the tension mode failure, which occurs when the distance between bolt holes is not large enough to bear the net tensile stress between neighboring holes. The failure mode in Figure 1 (b) indicates the shear mode failure, which occurs when the position of the bolt hole is close to the free edge of the plate. In general, tension or shear mode failure are regarded as undesirable behaviors in composite structures because they can lead to unstable and catastrophic failures. These types of failures can be prevented by optimizing the geometrical design around the bolt holes, as shown in Figures 2 and 3. When the geometries around the bolt holes are properly designed, the bearing mode failure occurs in accordance to the illustration in Figure 1 (c). In this mode, the fracture behavior tends to be stable, and consequently the strength can be maximized. Commonly, the thickness of the plate should be designed to be several times larger in the joint region than in other regions to improve the strength against bearing mode failure, as shown in Figure 4. However, these methods lead to an undesirable increase in the weight of composite structures.

Some researchers have proposed flexible fiber layouts around the bolt holes to avoid the aforementioned problem [1-13]. One of the feasible approaches was proposed by Kelly et al. [1-3], where the carbon fibers were aligned along the principle directions of the stress field around the bolt holes. However, more cost-effective and practical approaches are desirable considering the industrial benefits.

In this paper, a novel reinforcement technique using radial and circular layers (R-layer, C-layer) was studied to improve the strength and reliability of bolted joints, especially for large-scale composite parts, as shown in Figure 5. Experimental and numerical analyses were carried out to

investigate the effects of the R- and C-layers on the macroscopic strength and failure modes of the CFRP bolted joints.

Figure 1: Typical failure modes of bolted joints.

Figure 2: Optimization of geometries for tension mode failure.

Figure 3: Optimization of geometries for shear mode failure.

Figure 4: Optimization of geometries for bearing mode failure.

Figure 5: Optimized fiber patterns for reinforcement.

2 CONCEPT OF R- AND C-LAYERS

Figure 6 schematically shows the reinforcement mechanism of the R-layers. As shown in the Figure, the R-layer, where the carbon fibers are radially aligned, is expected to withstand the compressive stress around the bolt hole, and consequently to improve the strength against bearing mode failure. Moreover, the R-layer is expected to be functional at the initial stage of the macroscopic failure process. Figure 7 schematically shows the reinforcement mechanism of the C-layers. As shown in the figure, the C-layer, where the carbon fibers are circularly aligned, is expected to withstand the shear and tensile stress around the bolt hole and consequently to improve the strength against the shear mode failure. Moreover, the C-layer is expected to be functional at the ultimate stage of the macroscopic failure process.

3 MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

QI (Quasi-Isotropic) panels of a carbon/epoxy composite were fabricated as the base material using the RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process in accordance to the manufacture's recommended cure conditions. This material consists of the high-strength carbon fiber, T800SC (Toray), and the high-flow epoxy resin, RTM6 (Hexcel). The volume fraction of the carbon fiber was approximately 60%. Reinforced panels with R-layers (QI+R) and C-layers (QI+C) were also fabricated using the same process as QI panels. The nominal thicknesses, t , for the QI, QI+R and QI+C panels were respectively 2.56, 3.20 and 3.20 mm, corresponding to approximately 1/10 of the actual thicknesses of the target structural elements. Table 1 summarizes the configurations of specimens used in this paper.

As shown in Figure 8, two different types of geometries were investigated, to study the effects of the bolt hole positions, where the width, W , and the length, L , of the panels were respectively 100 and 290 mm. The diameter, d , of the hole was 25.4 mm. The position, e , of the hole was 76.2 or 25.4 mm. The specimens with $e/d = 3$ ($e = 76.2$ mm, $d = 25.4$ mm) have a typical geometry for bolted joints of composite materials where bearing mode failure can be expected. On the other hand, the specimen with $e/d = 1$ ($e = 25.4$ mm, $d = 25.4$ mm) has a peculiar geometry, where the bolt hole is closer to the free edge, and where shear failure should be concerned.

Figure 6: Expected reinforcement mechanism of R-layer.

Figure 7: Expected reinforcement mechanism of C-layer.

Specimen	Ply Pattern
QI	$[-45/0/45/90]_s$
QI+R	$[R/-45/0/45/90]_s$
QI+C	$[C/-45/0/45/90]_s$

Table 1: Configurations of specimens.

Figure 8: Geometries of specimens (unit: mm).

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

As shown in Figure 9, the tensile strength of the specimen was evaluated using a set of loading fixtures modeling a double-lap joint. The fastening torque of 95 N·m, which corresponds to approximately 1/10 of the recommended torque in the target structural elements, was applied to the steel bolt. Tensile loading was applied at a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min using a hydraulic testing machine, where the relative displacement of the steel bolt to the specimen was measured by a pair of CCD cameras, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: Schematic drawing of double-lap joint.

Figure 10: Experimental setup of double-lap joint.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1 LOAD-DISPLACEMENT RESPONSE

Figure 11 shows a typical load-displacement response for a QI specimen with $e/d = 3$. The ordinate represents the load applied to the specimen, P . The abscissa represents the displacement of the steel bolt, δ . The blue and red circles show the onset point of nonlinearity, P_{ini} , and the maximum point of load, P_{max} , respectively. As shown in the Figure, the load-displacement response was approximately linear during the early stages of loading. However, it turned slightly nonlinear after the onset point, P_{ini} . Microscopic observation of the specimens demonstrated that small-scale failure occurred locally in the vicinity of the bolt hole at the onset point, P_{ini} , resulting in the reduction of the stiffness of the specimen. On the other hand, large-scale failure occurred multiply in the specimen at the maximum point, P_{max} , as shown in later sections.

Figure 11: Typical load-displacement response of the QI specimen.

5.2 EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT ($e/d = 3$)

Figure 12 shows the macroscopic failure modes for the specimens with $e/d = 3$ at the maximum point, P_{\max} , obtained using the penetrant inspection technique. As shown in Figure 12 (a), bearing mode failure occurred in the QI specimen. In this case, multiple cracks formed near the edge of the bolt hole in the perpendicular direction to the loading line, suggesting that the compressive failure was caused by the normal stress, σ_{xx} . Similar mode failure occurred in the QI+R and QI+C specimens, as shown in Figures 12 (b) and (c). However, the distribution of the cracks was slightly different among the three types of tested specimens.

In this paper, the bearing strength, S_{bear} , of the specimen was determined from the experimental results using the following equation:

$$S_{\text{bear}} = \frac{P_{\text{appl}} - P_{\text{fric}}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where P_{appl} is the applied load to the specimen, which can be substituted by the onset load, P_{ini} , or the maximum load, P_{\max} . P_{fric} is the friction force between the specimen and the steel plates, which can be estimated from the axial force induced in the steel bolt. Therefore, the difference, $P_{\text{appl}} - P_{\text{fric}}$, can be considered to be approximately equal to the in-plane force, P_{bear} , applied to the edge of the bolt hole. Figure 13 shows the summary of the experimental results for the specimen with $e/d = 3$. The ordinate represents the bearing strength, S_{ini} , at the onset point, P_{ini} , or the bearing strength, S_{\max} , at the maximum point, P_{\max} . The initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , of the QI+R specimen was 16% higher than that of the QI specimen, while the strength of the QI+C specimen was 13% lower than that of the QI specimen, as shown in Figure 13 (a). On the other hand, the maximum bearing strengths, S_{\max} , of the QI+R and QI+C specimens were 30 and 28% higher than the strength of the QI specimen, as shown in Figure 13 (b).

Figure 12: Macroscopic failure modes of the specimens ($e/d = 3$).

Figure 13: Comparison of bearing strength ($e/d = 3$).

The above results demonstrated that the R-layer was effective in improving both of the initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , and the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} . However, the C-layer was effective only in improving the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} . These results were also consistent with the prediction discussed in Section 2.

5.3 EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT ($e/d = 1$)

Figure 14 shows the macroscopic failure modes for the specimens with $e/d = 1$ at the maximum point, P_{max} , obtained using the penetrant inspection technique. As shown in Figure 14 (a), shear mode failure occurred in the QI specimen. In the case straight cracks formed from the bolt hole to the free edge of the specimen. This was because the bolt hole was too close to the free edge of the specimen resulting in the increase of the shear stress, τ_{xy} , around the crack. Similar mode failure also occurred in the QI+R specimen, as shown in Figure 14 (b), whereas bearing mode failure occurred in the QI+C specimen, as shown in Figure 14 (c). This tendency was different from that observed for the specimens with $e/d = 3$. Figure 15 shows the summary of the experimental results for the specimens with $e/d = 1$. The ordinate represents the bearing strength, S_{ini} , at the onset point, P_{ini} , or the bearing strength, S_{max} , at the maximum point P_{max} . The initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , of the QI+R specimen was 13% lower than that of QI, while the initial strength of the QI+C specimen was almost the same as that of the QI specimen, as shown in Figure 15 (a). On the other hand, the maximum bearing strengths, S_{max} , of the QI+R and QI+C specimens were 8 and 36% higher than that of the QI specimen, as shown in Figure 15 (b).

The above results demonstrated that the C-layer prevented the shear failure caused by the inadequate geometry of the bolt hole, resulting in the improvement of the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} . However, the R-layer was not effective in preventing the shear mode failure. These results were also consistent with the prediction discussed in Section 2.

Figure 14: Macroscopic failure modes of the specimens ($e/d = 1$).

Figure 15: Comparison of bearing strengths ($e/d = 1$).

6 NUMERICAL PROCEDURES

The numerical analyses of the QI, QI+R and QI+C, specimens were carried out to study the effect of the R- and C-layers. Given the symmetry of the problem, 1/2 the model was used in this paper, as shown in Figure 16. The finite element code, MARC 2010, was used to perform the nonlinear stress analyses. Hashin's criterion and solid-shell elements were employed to estimate the anisotropic failure of the specimen. Tables 2 and 3 summarize the mechanical properties of the material.

Figure 16: Numerical model used in this study of double-lap joint.

T800SC/ RTM6			
Young modulus	E_L	164.0	[GPa]
	E_T	8.0	[GPa]
	E_Z	8.0	[GPa]
Shear modulus	G_{LT}	4.3	[GPa]
	G_{TZ}	2.8	[GPa]
	G_{ZL}	2.8	[GPa]
Poisson's ratio	ν_{LT}	0.34	
	ν_{TZ}	0.50	
	ν_{ZL}	0.02	

Table 2: Elastic modulus of the lamina.

T800SC/ RTM6			
Longitudinal tension	F_L^t	3300	[MPa]
Longitudinal compression	F_L^c	1600	[MPa]
Transverse tension	F_T^t	73	[MPa]
Transverse compression	F_T^c	214	[MPa]
In-plane shear	F_{LT}	79	[MPa]
Out-plane shear	F_{TZ}	46	[MPa]

Table 3: Strength of the lamina.

7 NUMERICAL ANALYSES RESULTS

7.1 EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT ($e/d = 3$)

Figure 17 shows a typical load-displacement response for a QI specimen with $e/d = 3$. The ordinate represents the load applied to the specimen, P . The abscissa represents the displacement of the steel bolt, δ . The blue and red circles show the onset point of nonlinearity, P_{ini} , and the maximum point of load, P_{max} , respectively. As shown in this figure, the initial failure was caused by the compressive stress, σ_{Lc} , in the longitudinal direction of the 45° layer, near the edge of the bolt hole. Figure 18 shows the stress distribution of the 45° layer on the inner surface of the bolt hole for the specimens with $e/d = 3$ at $P = 30$ kN. The ordinate represents the composite stress on the inner surface, σ_{Lc} . The abscissa represents the position on the inner surface, θ . The black line shows the numerical results for the QI specimen. The red and green lines respectively show the results for the QI+R and QI+C specimens. As shown in Figure 18, the fiber compressive stress, σ_{Lc} , was effectively reduced by the R-layer. Consequently, the initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , of the QI+R specimen was significantly higher than that of the QI specimen.

The above results agreed with the experimental results discussed in Section 5.2 where the effectiveness of the R-layer against bearing mode failure was demonstrated for the specimens with $e/d = 3$.

Figure 17: Load-displacement response obtained by the numerical analyses ($e/d = 3$, QI).

Figure 18: Distribution of fiber compressive stress on the 45° layer ($e/d = 3$, $P = 30$ kN).

7.2 EFFECT OF REINFORCEMENT ($e/d = 1$)

Figure 19 shows a typical load-displacement response for a QI specimen with $e/d = 1$. The ordinate represents the load applied to the specimen, P . The abscissa represents the displacement of the steel bolt, δ . The blue and red circles show the onset point of nonlinearity, P_{ini} , and the maximum point of load, P_{max} , respectively. As shown in the figure, the initial failure was caused by the shear stress, τ_{LT} , along the parallel direction of the 0° layer, near the edge of the bolt hole. Figure 20 shows the stress distribution of the 0° layer on the inner surface of the bolt hole for the specimens with $e/d = 1$ at $P = 21$ kN. The ordinate represents the shear stress on the inner surface, τ_{LT} . The abscissa represents the position on the inner surface, θ . The black line illustrates the numerical analyses results for QI specimen. The red and green lines respectively show the shear stresses for the QI+R and QI+C specimens. As shown in the figure, the shear stress, τ_{LT} , was reduced by the R- and C-layers. Consequently, the initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , of the QI+R and QI+C specimens was higher than that of QI.

The above results partly agreed with the experimental results discussed in Section 5.3, where the effectiveness of the C-layer against shear mode failure was demonstrated for the specimens with $e/d = 1$. However, the effect of the R-layer was not consistent as justified by the experimental and numerical analyses results.

Figure 19: Load-displacement response obtained by the numerical analyses ($e/d = 1$, QI).

Figure 20: Distribution of fiber shear stress on the 0° layer ($e/d = 1$, $P = 21$ kN).

8 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a novel reinforcement technique using radial and circular layers (R-layer, C-layer) was studied to improve the strength and reliability of bolted joints, especially for large-scale composite parts. Experimental and numerical analyses were carried out to investigate the effects of the R- and C-layers on the macroscopic strength and failure modes of the CFRP bolted joints. The result can be summarized as follows:

1. The experimental result for the specimen with $e/d = 3$ demonstrated that the R-layer was effective in improving both of the initial bearing strength, S_{ini} , and the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} . However, the C-layer was effective only in improving the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} .
2. The experimental result for the specimen with $e/d = 1$ demonstrated that the C-layer prevented the shear failure caused by the inadequate geometry of the bolt hole, resulting in the improvement of the maximum bearing strength, S_{max} . However, the R-layer was not effective in preventing the shear mode failure.
3. The numerical result for the specimen with $e/d = 3$ demonstrated that the effectiveness of the R-layer against bearing mode failure.
4. The numerical result for the specimen with $e/d = 1$ demonstrated that the effectiveness of the C-layer against shear mode failure.

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